

THE PRIMARY TOOL OF CINEMATOGRAPHY

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of the correct combination of the elements of the exposure triangle, and how it differs for certain reasons in photography and cinematography. The topic was researched using real-life examples and opinions of industry experts.

Keywords: cinematography, photographer, exposure, aperture, shutter speed, ISO.

ГЛАВНОЕ ОРУЖИЕ КИНООПЕРАТОРСКОГО ИСКУССТВА

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается важность правильного сочетания элементов экспозиционного треугольника, и чем он отличается по тем или иным причинам в фотографии и кинематографии. Тема исследована на реальных примерах и мнениях отраслевых экспертов.

Ключевые слова: кинематография, фотограф, выдержка, диафрагма, выдержка, ISO.

KINOOPERATORLIK SAN'ATINING ENG ASOSIY QUROLI

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O'zbekiston davlat san'at va madaniyat instituti

"Ovoz rejissyorligi va operatorlik mahorati"

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ekspozitsiya uchburchagi unsurlarini to‘g‘ri kombinatsiyalashning ahamiyati, uning fotografiya va kino san’atida ma’lum bir sabablarga ko‘ra farqlanishi haqida so‘z yuritilgan. Mavzu hayotiy misollar va soha mutaxassislarining fikr-mulohazalaridan foydalanilgan holda tadqiq etildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: kinematografiya, fotograf, ekspozitsiya, diafragma, shutter tezligi, ISO.

The literal meaning of the art of cinematography is depicted by light, because human’s eye does not see any image or environment in absolute darkness. Light is the most important factor in realizing the environment with human eyes. But even though the production of "light" is a powerful and profound phenomenon, there are only a few ways to control it in a film camera device for a film shot. The literal meaning of the art of cinematography is depicted by light, because in absolute nothingness, the human eye does not see any image or environment. Light is the most important factor in thinking about the environment with human eyes. But even though the production of "light" is a powerful and profound phenomenon, there are only a few ways to control it in a film camera device for a film shot.¹

In the field of cinematography, the manipulation of light is called "exposure". The word "exposure" comes from the Latin word for light. In cinematography and photography, there are two closely related ways of exposing an image according to the creator's imagination. The first is external (through lights and other auxiliary lighting devices); and the second is internal (through the "exposure triangle" of the film camera settings). Understanding the exposure triangle is one of the fundamentals of photography and filmmaking. Understanding the effects of Aperture, ISO, and Shutter Speed on exposure and other aspects of an image opens up many new creative approaches to image creation for the artist. In general, there is no such thing as a "perfect exposure" for every situation. Because the exposure of the image is the path chosen by the creator and the lighting stylistics, such as "low key" or "high key". For example, one creator can brightly depict a snowy scene in the general plan based on

¹ [THE INFLUENCE OF PAINTING ON THE VISUAL SOLUTION OF FEATURE FILMS](#)
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the given dramaturgy, while the other can depict it with a grayer and darker cold atmosphere. The correct combination of the elements of the exposure triangle is in the first place in creating any successful result.

If we look at the history of the invention of the film camera device, the only purpose of the first prototypes in it, It means that, the camera obscura, was to project the view of reality onto a flat plane. A camera obscura is a small pitch dark room with a single 1-4 mm radius hole. In it, the nature (being) behind that hole was projected onto the wall opposite to the hole of the camera obscura, It means that, the reflection of the image appeared on the wall. The exposure and clarity of the image in it was controlled by the size of the hole of the camera obscura. This is, of course, the first appearance and analogue of the working principle of the aperture of the camera lens, which is an element of the "exposure triangle".

Diaphragm or aperture is the opening and closing of the leaf-shaped hole between the lenses through which light passes. It is calibrated in f/stops or t/stops on film lenses and is usually specified in numbers such as 1.4, 2, 2.8, 4, 5.6, 8, 11, and 16. The lower the aperture number, the wider the aperture, allowing more light to pass through the lens and onto the film. A higher aperture number, on the other hand, means that the aperture is smaller and less light is passing through the lens. Along with exposure, brightness and darkness, aperture controls the depth of the image, or more precisely, how bright or blurry a certain area is in front of and behind the object or subject that the lens is focused on. In general, if we consider an image to be three-dimensional x, y, and depth z, rather than two-dimensional x and y, then the aperture determines how far along the z-dimension the sharpness is defined and how much the rest is obscured. The lower the aperture number, the larger the hole in the lens, and in turn, the less visible part of the image along the z-axis, the more blurry the background. The higher the f-number on the pointer, the smaller the hole in the lens and the longer the visible part of the image along the z-axis, and the sharper the background. Here, if we explain our point with a simple example, if two characters are placed back to back in relation to the camera and the focus is taken on the character It means that closer to the camera, the aperture controls how unclear or clear the character behind it is. Traditional

cinematographers and photographers refer to such a situation as the "out-of-focus level".

An important issue from the first steps of the development of projection of reality onto objects was to preserve the image reflected on the wall of the camera obscura for a long time. It means that, the image is not projected on the wall, but is recorded on special bottles that remember the image, and later, of course, on photo tapes. From these developing stages of photo technologies, two more elements of image exposure appeared, in addition to the lens aperture. They were the amount of time it took for the image and light to fall on the film and the amount of light sensitivity of the film. The principles of technical operation of this imaging are the same in today's film and photo devices. To put it more clearly, the element camera obscura, which means "dark room that reflecting the surroundings" in Latin, has turned into a small technical box due to the advanced development of techniques and technologies.

Khudoybergan Devonov, who started photographing his compatriots and Khiva's towers during the developing stages of photography and cinematography, put the object or subject he wants to photograph in front of the camera, and put the camera lens cover in front of them like his colleagues from all over the world. It only opened for a few seconds and then quickly closed. As mentioned above, the image in reality is the light for the image sensor in the camera device. It means that, the light falling on the tape through the camera lens is the image itself. If the time of falling of this light is not controlled, the tape is exposed to more time as well as an excessive amount of light. If the tape is not exposed to light for a long enough time, the image on the tape becomes dark. No matter how ridiculous it seemed in that days when photographers handled this process by hand, the properly exposed images they created are invaluable archives that bring the past to us today. Of course, breakthroughs in imaging technologies soon automated this computational and mechanical work of image creation. In cameras, a device called "zatvor" in Russian and "shutter" in English is placed between the lens and the tape. It allows you to control the time of the image exposure coming from the lens to the tape by opening and closing it. It means that, if the photographer sets the

shutter speed on the camera device to 1/50, the image is captured on the tape for 1/50 of a second, and the shutter opens and then closes for 1/50 of a second. ²

Frame is a combination of art and technical knowledge. Only after fully understanding the basics of these two aspects can one express creative views in the image. Photographer Jeff Carlson notes that in addition to controlling exposure with shutter speed, there are two things that can be easily achieved in a creative approach to photography. The first is time-freezing, It means that, freezing any action in milliseconds in phase without any blurring. If the shutter speed is set to speeds like 1/1000 second, it opens and closes quickly and captures exactly that millisecond part of the image regardless of the motion. For example, the image of a car racing at a speed of 160 km/s is captured clearly, without any blur despite the high speed. And the second, depending on the creative thinking and the situation being depicted, the creator can make the shutter speed slower than the normal perception of the human eye. In this case, the blur that appears in the image can be used for the purpose of brightening the image or creating other creative stylistics. In particular, the above-mentioned example of a car moving at a speed of 160 km/s in such a state, the body and wheels are blurred along its line of motion until they are almost invisible, and its lights that are on are an image is depicted as a line across. The most famous of such images was taken under the Big Ben clock in London, United Kingdom. It shows a clock, a night landscape, and long lines of red traffic lights along the bridge.

As the real image is captured on the tape by passing through the wavelength of light, complex lens and aperture, one of the important factors in how the image is illuminated is the quality of the tape. As a result of the popularization of photo and film films, the diversity of film types and the properties of different color and light sensitivity have increased. The light sensitivity of the tape is designated by the international standardization organization (the name of the organization that sets the light sensitivity standards in cinema) with the letters "ISO". Although this term

² [CAMERAMAN'S SKILL IN MAKING A DOCUMENTARY FILMS](#)

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originated in the film era, it still refers to the light sensitivity of the matrix in digital photography.

ISO is perhaps the most obscure and least understood element in exposureometry. Although the ISO meter changes lightness or darkness in the concept of exposure, an additional aspect is to control the level of visual noise in the image. If the ISO indicator is set to the minimum from the camera settings, for example 50 iso or 100 iso, then the image is created cleanly without visual noise on the tape or on the display. At the same time, a low ISO indicator indicates low light sensitivity, which means that it will be difficult to shoot at night and indoors when there is no or no artificial lighting equipment. In order for a well-exposed image to appear on a low-sensitivity film or matrix, the subject or object being photographed must be very bright. However, if the ISO indicator is set to the maximum or higher than 1600 iso, it indicates that the sensitivity of the tape or matrix has increased to light. In this case, a well-exposed image will appear due to the light sensitivity of the tape, even if the environment and the object being photographed are not very bright. However, higher ISO values result in increased visual noise in the image. In most cases, images and frames with excessive visual noise are considered unusable. Nevertheless, a large percentage of cinematographers consider it a "plastic" frame if there is not enough visual noise in the frame. At the time when the ISO standard was established, world cinema was at the same stage of development. During the era of the great classics and tapes, most Hollywood film was recorded on Kodak tapes marked with 800 ISO. That's why today's cinematographers claim that natural visual noise appears at 800 ISO. The brightness of the image and its visual noise do not have a clearly defined ISO indicator for any situation, the cinematographer or photographer determines how to decide based on his chosen creative path.³

The correct combination of the above-mentioned elements of exposition is the most important in the optimal exposition of dramaturgy. Although both aperture,

³ [DEVELOPMENT OF POETIC STYLE IN UZBEK CINEMATOGRAPHY](#)/K Khidirova - Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and ..., 2022

shutter speed, and ISO have an effect on the exposure of the image, they each have additional factors of influence. This situation means that there is no universal way to expose the image. A question arises: from which element should the exposition begin?

When setting the aperture, shutter speed and iso indicators, which are the elements of the exposure triangle, the operator or photographer focuses on the priority in the meaning of the reality he is photographing. If the photographer is photographing a model of clothing against a background of colored paper, it is a priority for him to make the colored paper with a low aperture and at the same time a wider aperture to make it vague, dull and monotonous, and the model and clothes are clean blue without visual noise. ISO indicators are set as low as possible. In this case, if the photographer is shooting with the camera in his hand, it is important to set the shutter speed to approximately 1/125 second so that hand shake does not cause the image to blur. But the combination of elements of the exposure triangle in a film frame is different. For example, as we have seen in several films, the first character in the foreground of the shot looks towards the camera with a certain emotion, and in the background, another character reacts to the emotion of the first one. In the exposure of such a frame composition, the priority is in most cases in the aperture, It means that, in the case of making both of the two characters standing with a certain distance in terms of the depth of the frame clear, clear or clearer, the aperture indicator will be in larger numbers, It means that, the lens aperture is set to a small size. The other two elements of exposure are determined by the level of illumination after the aperture. In addition, a number of cinematographers who are master at their field give importance to the mental impact of visual noise on the viewer. In the works of many c.⁴

If we look at the creators' works who are participating in the Cannes International Film Festival, the films were shot from start to finish at 400, 800, or even 1600 ISO indicators. The priority of the exposure triangle is the ISO indicator in the first place

⁴ [Creative researches of young cameramen on the creation of graphic image in modern uzbek feature films](#)M Ikboljon, KS Tirkashaliyevich - International Journal of Engineering and Advanced ..., 2019

for these creators, and the other two elements are determined depending on the dramaturgy of the image and lighting.

The goal of working attentively on each compositional exposure is to capture your subject in a way that expresses your artistic vision. Image is a form of art, both in the form of photography and in the form of cinematography. It does not have any limits. Therefore, the creator's image does not necessarily suit the definition of "correct exposure". It can be unnatural, darker and duller, or lighter than normal. The most important thing is that the image is able to convey the story and emotions felt by the creator to the viewer.

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